

On the delay of O-RAN Fronthaul: A methodology based on Generalized Jackson Networks

Fátima Khan[†], Óscar Gil[¶], Luis Diez[†], Elena Serna[¶], Ramón Agüero[†]

[†]*Universidad de Cantabria*, Santander, Spain. {khanf@unican.es, {ldiez, ramon}@tmat.unican.es

[¶]*Telefónica*, Madrid, Spain. {oscar.gillucia, elena.sernasantiago}@telefonica.com

Abstract—The Open-Fronthaul (O-FH) is a Time Sensitive Network (TSN) segment within the Open-RAN (O-RAN) architecture, where the legacy base station is disaggregated following the 7.2x functional split. One of the strategic objectives sought by network operators is to foster the centralization of the Open - Distributed Unit (O-DU), to serve multiple remote sites. Hence, ensuring an accurately modeling of the fronthaul performance becomes critical, due to its stringent timing requirements. In this work, we propose a novel modeling methodology, based on Generalized Jackson Networks (GJN), to derive key performance metrics such as waiting time and utilization. Additionally, we apply Kingman’s approximation to evaluate delay percentiles under high traffic load conditions. This analytical method allows for fast and scalable performance evaluation, avoiding the need for extensive packet-level simulations, which become computationally prohibitive as traffic load steadily increases. Our results evince that under sensible operating situations, the proposed approach yields rather precise results, providing an upper performance bound.

Index Terms—Fronthaul, heavy traffic, dimensioning, O-RAN

I. INTRODUCTION

The proper dimensioning of future mobile networks, particularly fronthaul networks, has become a critical task for operators. Fronthaul segment, especially in the context of Open - Fronthaul (O-FH) as defined by the Open-RAN (O-RAN) architecture, poses unique challenges due to the stringent latency and bandwidth requirements. One of the most demanding aspects of the fronthaul, which connects Open - Distributed Unit (O-DU) and Open - Radio Unit (O-RU), is the precise alignment of transmission and reception intervals (time windows) to ensure proper coordination [1], thereby avoiding Time Alligment Error (TAE) [2].

O-FH traffic takes the highest priority when it coexists with other technologies and flows [3], and the enhanced Common Public Radio Interface (eCPRI) used by the O-FH introduces variability in packet size [4]. Traditional traffic modeling approaches, such as those based on Poisson assumptions, fall short in capturing the true behavior of O-FH traffic. Unlike conventional packet-switched traffic, O-FH traffic exhibits deterministic periodicity in its transmission timing, due to the configuration of the underlying radio. However, it also presents variability in packet payload sizes. This variability arises from the dynamic allocation of Physical Resource Blocks (PRB), which are not always fully utilized. As a result, the bitrate may present rapid fluctuations, even if the transmission intervals themselves remain constant. These characteristics give rise to non-Poissonian traffic patterns, particularly under realistic

operating conditions. As a result, simplified models based on memoryless arrivals (and so exponential inter-arrival times) fail to capture the distinctive features of O-FH traffic, leading to inaccurate estimations of key performance indicators, such as queuing delay, which is strongly influenced by Packet Delay Variation (PDV), and traffic load variation, which are critical factors in the proper design of time window alignment. Furthermore, the evolution of O-RAN architectures towards centralized topologies implies pooling processing functions, where an O-DU manages a set of O-RUs, so increasing traffic aggregation, further emphasizing the need for accurate modeling and proper network dimensioning tools.

We propose leveraging Generalized Jackson Networks (GJN) models, which can accurately capture the statistical properties of O-FH traffic, thereby enabling more reliable performance analysis and resource dimensioning. In addition, using Kingman’s approximation, we can accurately estimate delay percentiles under high traffic load conditions, a critical factor when dimensioning Time Sensitive Network (TSN), where stringent latency bounds must be maintained. To that aim, this work proposes a novel methodology to evaluate network performance under varying levels of functional centralization and architectural design choices. Our main contributions are:

- We introduce a methodology to characterize delay and its variability in O-FH networks, considering factors such as queuing and transmission delays across multi-hop topologies to meet the temporal constraints imposed by the O-FH interface, thereby supporting informed decision-making during the network planning phase.
- We apply two complementary approaches: (i) GJN models, and (ii) Kingman’s approximation, to estimate network performance under high traffic load conditions.
- We show the feasibility of the proposed methodology on a realistic fronthaul topology, using traffic patterns that accurately reflect the inherent variability of O-FH traffic in this network segment, mimicking real site configurations.

The paper is structured as follows: Section II reviews the state of the art and identifies the research gap that we tackle in this work. Section III discusses the theoretical background used to analyze network’s performance. Section IV outlines the methodology we propose and highlights the key metrics involved in the design of time window alignment. Section V validates the proposed methodology over a reference scenario, and in Section VI the results obtained over a realistic setup are

discussed. Finally, Section VII concludes the paper, highlighting the most insightful outcomes and outlining future research directions.

II. STATE OF ART

Despite the increasing adoption of the Cloud Radio Access Network (C-RAN) architecture, leading to an extended fronthaul segment within mobile networks, there is a clear lack of studies that address this scenario under the O-RAN specification.

Sehier et al. analyze in [5] the jitter introduced by switching nodes in fronthaul networks and provide dimensioning guidelines, focusing on the UpLink (UL) and the limitations imposed by the rigid Common Public Radio Interface (CPRI) protocol. In addition, Otero et al. investigate in [6] and [7] Ethernet-based packet-switched fronthaul networks, and they propose using high-percentile queuing delays derived from the G/G/1 queuing model as a dimensioning metric. This approach aims to increase fronthaul link distances, while respecting strict latency requirements. Similarly, Artuso et al. discuss in [8] dimensioning results based on both analytical modeling and discrete-event simulations. In [9] the authors introduce Heuristic RND (HRND), a novel methodology that incorporates real-world open data, numerology, and bandwidth allocation to guide network design toward optimized coverage, capacity, Quality of Experience (QoE), and cost trade-offs. Mathew et al. propose in [10] exploiting network calculus to derive delay bounds in integrated fronthaul and backhaul 5G networks, with a particular focus on C-RAN. Furthermore, Lagén et al. explore in [11] modulation compression techniques as a means to reduce fronthaul capacity demands, showing that significant bandwidth savings can be achieved with minimal degradation in performance.

All aforementioned works analyze various methods to stretch fronthaul capabilities, while maintaining performance. However, they largely overlook scenarios where fronthaul networks comprise multi-hop topologies within the operator transport aggregation network, where a centralized O-DU serves a pool of distributed O-RUs. Such centralized configurations introduce new challenges related to transmission distances and their impact on timing coordination, especially over the synchronization of time windows between O-DU and O-RU. These aspects have not been thoroughly explored within the current O-RAN framework, posing an open research question which we tackle in this paper.

III. BACKGROUND

GJN is a class of queuing networks that allows using renewal arrival processes that are not necessarily Poisson, and independent and identically distributed (i.i.d) service times that do not need to follow exponential distributions. On the other hand, unlike classical Jackson networks, GJN do not always admit explicit analytical solutions.

In a GJN, there are J single-server nodes. Packets arrive exogenously at node j following a certain renewal process with

rate $\alpha_j \geq 0$. Service at each node assumes a First-In First-Out (FIFO) discipline, while service times at node j form an i.i.d sequence with mean m_j , and so rate $\mu_j = 1/m_j$. Upon completing service at node i , a packet is routed to node j with probability p_{ij} . Matrix $P = [p_{ij}] \in \mathbb{R}^{J \times J}$ is referred to as the routing matrix.

Under heavy-traffic conditions, the queue length process can be approximated by a Reflected Brownian Motion (RBM) in the positive orthant \mathbb{R}_+^J . The approximation takes the form:

$$Q(t) = X(t) + RY(t), \quad (1)$$

subject to the following conditions:

$$Q(t) \geq 0, \quad (2)$$

$$dY(t) \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad Y(0) = 0, \quad (3)$$

$$Q_j(t) dY_j(t) = 0, \quad j = 1, \dots, J. \quad (4)$$

where $Q(t) \in \mathbb{R}_+^J$ is the vector of queue lengths at time t . Furthermore, $X(t)$ corresponds to a Brownian motion that can be described by a *drift* vector $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^J$, representing the network input load, and the covariance matrix $\Gamma \in \mathbb{R}^{J \times J}$, capturing variability in arrivals, service times and routing. On the other hand, $Y(t) \in \mathbb{R}^J$ is a non-decreasing regulator process that increases only when some component of $Q(t)$ equals zero, as seen in Eqs. (3) and (4). Last, $R = I - P'$ is the reflection matrix, which specifies the reflection direction at the boundary [12, Chapter 7]. Table I presents a summary of the key variables in the system, along with their dependencies.

TABLE I: Notation used in the GJN described as a RBM

Symbol	Definition
J	Number of single-server nodes in the network
P	Routing matrix
R	Reflection matrix, $R = (I - P')^{-1}$, where P' being the transpose
α	Vector of exogenous arrival rate
λ	Vector of total arrival rates, $\lambda = (I - P')^{-1}\alpha$
μ_j, m_j	Service rate, $\mu_j = 1/m_j$ and service time at node j
ρ_j	Traffic intensity at node j , $\rho_j = \lambda_j/\mu_j$
$X(t)$	Brownian motion capturing stochastic fluctuations
θ	Drift vector, $\theta = \alpha \cdot (I - P) \cdot \mu$
Γ	Covariance matrix of $X(t)$
$Y(t)$	Regulator process, increasing only when $Q_j(t) = 0$
$Q(t)$	Queue length process at time t
\mathcal{L}	Differential operator, where $\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}(\theta, \Gamma)$
\mathcal{D}_j	Directional derivative, where $\mathcal{D}_j = \mathcal{D}(r_j)$

The queue process admits a RBM approximation when the stability condition $R^{-1}\theta < 0$ holds, which is equivalent to $(I - P')^{-1}\alpha < \mu$ or $\rho_j < 1$ for all j . In this regime, the stationary distribution π satisfies the Basic Adjoint Relation (BAR), a Partial Differential Equation (PDE) shown in Eq. (5), which balances interior dynamics ($\mathcal{L}f$) against boundary corrections ($\mathcal{D}_j f$):

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}_+^J} \mathcal{L}f d\pi + \sum_{j=1}^J \int_{F_j} \mathcal{D}_j f \nu_j(dz) = 0 \quad (5)$$

where ν_j are boundary measures, absolutely continuous with respect to the Lebesgue measure on F_j , and π represents the

stationary distribution of the queue length process $Q(t)$ under the heavy-traffic Brownian approximation. This distribution describes the long-run probabilistic behavior of the system, and satisfies the BAR by balancing the internal dynamics of the network and the boundary reflections. The solution structure critically depends on the traffic intensities θ and the variability parameters Γ , as defined in [12, Section 7.4], with product-form solutions only in purely exponential (memoryless) situations [13]. For general distributions, numerical methods such as QNET [13] can be employed to derive queuing delay, $\mathbb{E}[W_j]$, approximations, where $\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$ denotes the expected value. Hence, to obtain the average sojourn time at each node j , we use the expression, $\mathbb{E}[S_j] = \mathbb{E}[W_j] + m_j$. Once the delay for each node in the network has been computed, the one-way End-to-End (E2E) delay for the overall fronthaul segment for any traffic flow $f \in F$, where F denotes the set of all flows, can be expressed as $\tau_f = \sum_{j \in P(f)} \mathbb{E}[S_j]$ where $P(f)$ represents the set of nodes traversed by flow f .

Furthermore, to analyze the variability of the delay for O-FH traffic, we propose applying Kingman's Law to estimate corresponding percentiles p under high saturation conditions [7]. By considering the network's decomposition, we identify and select those links that are balanced-loaded ($\rho_j \rightarrow 1$) as bottleneck links. The corresponding approximation is given by:

$$W_q^{(p)} = \max \left\{ 0, \frac{\mathbb{E}[S]}{1-\rho} \frac{C^2[\mathbb{T}] + C^2[S]}{2} \cdot \log \left(\frac{\rho}{1-p} \right) \right\} \quad (6)$$

where $C^2[\mathbb{T}]$ and $C^2[S]$ are the Squared coefficient of variation (SCV) of the inter-arrival times and packet sizes.

IV. CHARACTERIZATION METHODOLOGY

As mentioned earlier we propose a novel methodology to tackle the dimensioning of specific networking scenarios, particularly focusing on situations with stringent latency constraints, as it is the case for fronthaul networks. Fig. 1 illustrates the proposed workflow to carry out a comprehensive characterization of network performance. The analysis begins by examining the inherent characteristics of the fronthaul network, which exhibits a deterministic transmission schedule, due to the strict alignment of O-DU and O-RU transmission and reception intervals. Although transmission timing is deterministic, packet sizes vary according to resource allocation decisions. Consequently, O-FH traffic might be affected by parameters such as Subcarrier Spacing (SCS), Bandwidth (BW), compression settings, Time Division Duplex (TDD) patterns and the number of transmission layers.

To appropriately compute the traffic load injected by the O-DU in DownLink (DL) mode, as depicted in Figure 1, we must consider that the packet size is determined by the number of resource blocks allocated by the MAC scheduler, N_{RB} , from a total value depending on the SCS and BW. Each PRB carries IQ samples whose size depends on the compression algorithm applied, for instance Block Floating Point 9 (BFP9), which significantly impacts the resulting data volume. This compression technique changes the number of bits used per IQ sample, reducing the overall size of the fronthaul packets.

The total traffic rate is obtained by multiplying the per-layer rate by the number of active layers, N_{layer} , in each O-RU:

$$R = \frac{N_{\text{layer}} \cdot N_{RB} \cdot B(w_{\text{data}} \cdot N_{sc} \cdot 2 + f) \cdot N_{\text{symb}} \cdot 2^\mu \cdot 8}{T_{\text{subframe}}} \quad (7)$$

where w_{data} is the number of bits per IQ component, N_{sc} is the number of subcarriers per PRB, f represents the overhead associated with the compression scheme, N_{symb} is the number of OFDM symbols per slot, and μ denotes the numerology index. The function $B(\cdot)$ converts the quantity from bits to bytes and is used to express the size of the eCPRI packet payload. A detailed derivation of this formula and its practical implications in the eCPRI context can be found in [14]. Based on this accurate estimation of the data volume introduced by O-FH traffic, the network can be properly dimensioned.

Fig. 1: Diagram of the methodology workflow, integrating the ns-3 simulator and the QNET solver, along with the key parameters involved in designing the alignment of the time windows.

Based on the network topology and the traffic obtained from datasets, simulations, or synthetic generators, the performance can be characterized in terms of delay, as depicted in Fig. 1. For this purpose, it is necessary to collect timestamp traces corresponding to packet generation events, as well as the associated packet sizes. When multiple traffic flows are injected into the same node, they are aggregated and treated as a single flow. From the resulting traces, the following metrics are extracted. For each packet i , we define: (i) t_i^{TX} , the transmission timestamp, and (ii) s_i , the packet size in bytes. The interarrival time between consecutive packets is calculated as: $d_i = t_{i+1}^{\text{TX}} - t_i^{\text{TX}}$, $\forall i \in \{1, \dots, n-1\}$, and the vector of interarrival times is given by: $\mathbb{T} = \{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_{n-1}\}$. Similarly, the packet size vector is defined as: $P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n\}$.

We can now compute the key statistical descriptors required for delay modeling: (i) the arrival rate $\lambda = 1/\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{T}]$, (ii) SCV of the interarrival times $C^2[\mathbb{T}] = \text{Var}(\mathbb{T})/\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{T}]^2$ (iii) SCV of

the packet sizes $C^2[P] = \text{Var}(P)/\mathbb{E}[P]^2$. The average service time is estimated by considering the average packet length and the transmission capacity C of the corresponding egress link. These statistical metrics are then used as input parameters in a queuing-based delay model, such as QNET, allowing us to perform an analytical characterization of the delay under varying load conditions and different network topologies. In this sense QNET is exploited to numerically solve the PDE, yielding the waiting queue time at each node. With this result, we can finally compute the average one-way delay per packet, as it traverses the network.

This analytical delay modeling becomes particularly relevant in the context of O-RAN deployments, which are governed by strict timing constraints due to the time-sensitive nature of the corresponding interfaces. As illustrated in Fig. 1, O-FH interfaces handle eCPRI delays, using specific reference points to measure timing metrics. A strict alignment between Transmission Window (TW) and Reception Window (RW) is crucial to meet timing requirements imposed by the O-RU and underlying network. We thus consider transport delay within a bounded range, where the minimum value includes propagation, transmission and switching times, while the greatest delay adds the variations caused by network load and traffic dynamics. To avoid TAE, it is necessary to ensure that $RW \geq TW + DL_{var}$, where RW is constrained by the hardware design of the O-RU. Specifically, the RW must be long enough to capture the DL variability (DL_{var}) caused by fronthaul network impairments, as well as to accommodate the complete transmission of the corresponding symbol.

V. VALIDATION

In this section, we validate the proposed methodology by performing extensive simulation-based experiments with synthetically generated traffic, using the ns-3 simulator to accurately assess network performance. To evaluate whether the proposed methodology is able to accurately capture network behavior, we conducted several tests using different traffic patterns over a tandem network with two hops, as depicted in Fig. 2. The egress port capacities of the two nodes are set to 70 Gbps and 10 Gbps, respectively. In addition, the scenario assumes the use of jumbo frames, thereby avoiding fragmentation.

The traffic injected by the O-DU models a multi-cell site configuration with multiple combinations of SCS and BW. To highlight the impact of adopting a stochastic traffic model versus a more deterministic and bounded alternative, we define and evaluate three different scenarios, as shown in Table II, considering the FR1 range with BFP9 (cf. [14, Table I]; O-RAN [4]). Hence, the inter-arrival time column reflects the combined behavior of different SCS, whereas the packet size is directly related to PRB_{use} . In all cases the average packet size of 3000B (resulting from $PRB_{use} = 50\%$ across a mix of configurations), and the maximum packet sizes does not exceed 8000B. Then we increase the traffic generated by the O-DU, in terms of traffic intensity ρ , relative to the 10 Gbps capacity of the egress port.

Fig. 2: Scenario setup and traffic patterns reflecting 5G NR resource allocation and eCPRI protocol characteristics.

TABLE II: Traffic model distributions

Scenario	Inter-arrival Time	Packet Size
(a)	Exponential	Exponential $[0, \infty]B$
(b)	Exponential	Bounded exponential $[0, 8000]B$
(c)	Constant (fixed)	Uniform $[0, 6000]B$

As shown in Fig. 3, QNET accurately computes the average benchmark values of the one-way delay for the three scenarios, assuming each node as a G/G/1, almost perfectly matching the results obtained with the simulation (greenish circles within the boxplots). Furthermore, if we focus on the results for the highest load values (zoom area at each figure), we can see that the bounds yielded by the Kingman's Law Eq. (6), for the most congested egress port captures quite well the observed behavior, and each percentile value matches the corresponding part of the boxplot. On the other hand, we also see that, when the traffic distribution becomes more deterministic (fewer merging flows), the Kingman's Law yields an upper bound, which becomes less tight when the load is higher.

VI. EVALUATION

This section considers two site configurations, analyzing their impact, as well as that of the resulting traffic load over the network performance. In configuration (a), there is a tri-sectorial site with three cells. One sector uses C-band configured with MIMO (32T32R), BW (100 MHz), and SCS (30 kHz), while the other use B1/B3 bands configured with MIMO (4T4R), BW (10 MHz), and SCS (15 kHz). Configuration (b) comprises a single cell, where the B1/B3 bands remain unchanged, and the C-band is configured with MIMO (4T4R). As a result of the (32T32R) configuration in (a), we multiplex 16 layers, whereas in (b), with the (4T4R) configuration, only 4 layers are multiplexed. In all cases, the capacity of the interfaces has been established based on the maximum load capacity injected per site, along with a potential centralization degree at the Hierarchical Level 4 (HL4) level, considering the interconnection of 7 sites with identical configurations. Hence, 700G and 100G interfaces are used for configuration (a), and 70G and 10G for configuration (b).

(a) Exponential inter-arrival times and packet sizes.

(b) Exponential inter-arrival times, bounded exponential packet sizes.

(c) Constant inter-arrival times, uniform packet sizes.

Fig. 3: One-way delay in a two-hop tandem network.

The load was systematically varied, by adjusting the minimum required percentage of PRBs utilization. We assume that the O-RU behavior (packet size) is modeled with a uniform distribution as a result of how resources are handled, as depicted in Fig. 4. It is worth noting that, when PRB_{min} equals 0, the O-RU operates in average at 50% load. On the other hand, increasing the minimum PRB utilization leads to a higher load, as each transmission opportunity requires, at least, PRB_{min} to be used. To isolate the effects of configuration and load, other parameters were kept constant in the experiments: all available symbols were utilized, and the packet transmission frequency was also fixed, according to the configured SCS and BW, as well as PRB_{max} . Experimental results are obtained through simulations conducted in *ns-3*, with durations of 10 seconds and 1 second for configurations (a) and (b), respectively. Each flow produces on the order of 10^5 packet samples. Analytical results are derived using *QNET*, modeling each node as either *M/M/1* or *G/G/1*.

Fig. 5 shows the one-way delay, using a logarithmic scale. The shaded green area represents the Interquartile Range

Fig. 4: Resource distribution in the 5G NR grid configuration.

(IQR), and the lighter shaded area represent the values of 1.5 times IQR. Rounded markers are the average values obtained with the simulation. The red plot shows the results that were obtained with traditional Jackson networks theory, where each node is modeled as an *M/M/1* queue, while the yellowish plot shows the results obtained when each node is modeled as a *G/G/1* queue. We increase the minimum PRB_{use} and we keep the maximum value at the overall available resources. This makes the load at each site higher, and it also reduces the variability, since the corresponding uniform distribution has a narrower range, as illustrated in Fig. 5. As can be observed in Figs. 5a and 5b, the shaded area shows how increasing the minimum resource usage leads to the saturation of available resources, contributing to reduce the PDV variability.

In addition, the results for both configurations, Fig. 5a and 5b, clearly evince how dimensioning impacts network delay when a small site is considered (upper figure), and the interfaces are properly dimensioned according to the maximum load capacity. As can be seen, *G/G/1* provides more accurate results, and it better fits the trend observed in the simulation results, which correspond to the most realistic values. However, as the distribution of packet size gets closer to a constant value, the error becomes more relevant. On the other hand, the error observed when modeling each node as an *M/M/1* queue is always higher, since this model assumes a greater variability for both inter-arrival and service processes.

It is worth mentioning that in this particular case, the Kingman's Law does not yield a very accurate result, as an increase of traffic intensity, ρ , leads to a reduction of its variability. Kingman's approximation, which is valid for *G/G/1* queues, assumes that arrival and service processes are stochastic. However, when the minimum payload is increased and so the traffic variability decreases (in this case, the load gets closer to saturation levels), the stochastic assumption of the model does not hold. As a result, the approximation becomes less accurate, leading to more significant discrepancies between the predicted delay percentiles and the observed simulation results.

To sum up, when dimensioning a network with limited processing capacity at the interfaces, which might be rather typical of small-site deployments, the increased service time makes queuing delay a more dominant factor. In such cases, values obtained with traditional Jackson network models can significantly mislead the dimensioning process, whereas employing a generalized Jackson network notably reduces this

(a) Three-cells, Three-Sectorial, 4T4R in Bands B1/B3 and 32T32R in Band C

(b) Cell, Three-Sectorial, Bands B1/B3/C or Trisectorial 4T4R Configuration

Fig. 5: One-way delay versus Minimum PRB use (%) in a two-hop tandem network.

error and so provides a more accurate representation of traffic variability.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

We have addressed the challenges related to strict time alignment and latency management in Open Fronthaul networks, highlighting the need of counting on accurate network dimensioning tools to meet the stringent performance requirements imposed by O-RAN-based architectures. We propose leveraging queuing theory, specifically Kingman’s approximation and concepts from Generalized Jackson Networks, to analyze delay percentiles under high-load conditions, as well as the average network performance.

To support this analysis, we thoroughly characterize O-FH traffic patterns under FR1 conditions. This allows us to tackle the modeling of each node as a G/G/1 queue. We also use the ns-3 simulator to validate the proposed theoretical model, comparing delay distributions obtained from realistic traffic traces. The results indicate that the analytical framework tightly bounds the overall delay, in contrast to the M/M/1 model. In this sense, this framework can be used for early-stage network design and performance estimation. Additionally, the results also show that Kingman’s approximation is only valid when the traffic exhibits minimum stochastic characteristic.

As future work, we plan to extend this analysis over a real testbed to capture the dynamic behavior of fronthaul traffic under varying load conditions. We also aim to obtain traces from the 5G-LENA module of ns-3 to simulate more complex radio scenarios. The ultimate goal would be to explore the use of Generalized Jackson Networks in network planning processes, considering more realistic deployment constraints.

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